

Role of Probiotics in Prevention and Treatment of Colon Cancer

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Abstract

Cancer is one of the fatal conditions whose treatment is still in doubt. Various synthetic agents and (standard) chemotherapeutic drugs in treating cancer are not efficient. Researchers are trying to find competent clinical management for cancer as synthetic agents develop drug resistance, affect the quality of life, and are also not affordable to the patients. The purpose of this study is to highlight the importance of probiotics in preventing and treating cancer. Probiotics are actually living organisms that provide health benefits to the hosts (when administrated). Probiotics help control urogenital infection and diarrhea, alleviate lactose intolerance, reduce the level of cholesterol, and relieve the patients from bowel syndrome. Due to antioxidant potential, probiotics are beneficial for treating chronic diseases like cancer. The use of probiotics as vital dietary supplements is efficient in managing the side effects of radiation therapy, chemotherapy, and surgery. Proper administration of probiotics can reduce the inflammation of intestinal mucosa as they rebalance the gut microbiota and modulate the immunity of the gastrointestinal tract. Probiotics metabolome interferes in the progression of colon cancer. Short-lived metabolites (from milk) after getting fermented with *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* strains have efficient role in neutralizing the risk factors of colon

carcinogenesis. Due to the ingestion of probiotics, those components that are genotoxic to the colon are excreted in small concentrations from urine, and those components that encourage oxidized DNA bases are excreted in high concentrations. Therefore, research on the anti-carcinogenic property along with the mechanism of action (particularly in treatment) of specific probiotics is desirable and important. Clinical trials should be conducted for the approval of probiotics validation as an alternative to colon cancer therapy from the medical community.

Keywords: Probiotics, Colon cancer, Lactic acid bacteria, Colon cancer risk, Gut microbiota